

ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE STIFFNESS-CRITICAL BONDED JOINTS

Peter M. Wegner, Ph.D.
Jeffrey S. Welsh, Ph.D.*
Air Force Research Laboratory/VSSV
3550 Aberdeen Ave SE, Bldg. 472
Kirtland AFB, NM 87117-5776, USA

John A. Lips
California Polytechnic State University
San Luis Obispo, CA, USA

* Corresponding Author

SUMMARY: Most space structures require very high stiffness to overcome the absence of passive damping that exists in the atmosphere encompassing earth-borne structures. Generally very high modulus carbon fiber composite materials are used in these structures to ensure the components have the highest possible stiffness. The problem arises when these very stiff structures are joined together through the use of adhesively bonded joints. The effect on the overall structural stiffness due to these bonded joints is not well understood. An in-depth analytical and experimental study was conducted to examine the loss of stiffness resulting from adhesively bonded joints. Comparisons were made between numerical models and experimental results and recommendations for modeling bonded joints in space structures were developed.

KEYWORDS: space structures, bonded joints, stiffness, finite element analysis, lap joint

INTRODUCTION

The unique operating environment of space often dictates that, at least from a structural perspective, the structural stiffness is the limiting design variable. This unique requirement is a result of both the microgravity environment and the near vacuum conditions experienced by an object in orbit around the earth. In these conditions space structures do not experience high gravitational loads and so strength margins are generally very high. However, there is very little atmospheric damping or gravity acting on these structures so vibrations can continue for long periods of time. In order to minimize the displacement induced by these vibrations and to increase the controllability of the system, very high structural stiffness is required. This phenomenon is perhaps most easily illustrated by the demanding stiffness requirements imposed on many space-based systems. Often high-modulus carbon fiber reinforced composite materials are required to achieve the desired performance. Unfortunately, one common approach used to join multiple composite structural components is to bond them together with an epoxy adhesive. A great deal of work has been expended in the aircraft industry to improve the strength of adhesively bonded joints; much less effort has been expended quantifying the associated stiffness loss.¹⁻⁵ That is, concerns associated with a loss of stiffness when individual stiffness-critical components are adhesively joined together to form a system have largely been ignored, presumably because the ever-increasing performance requirements of stiffness-critical structures have only recently exposed this oversight.

For these reasons, the objective of the current study was to develop an understanding of the stiffness characteristics of bonded joints and to develop numerical techniques capable of accurately modeling and predicting the static and dynamic response of these joints. Being able to accurately characterize the dynamic response of stiffness-critical structures is hindering the development of appropriate design practices for these systems and can result in inability to maintain stability and control⁶.

Because of the computational difficulties associated with finite element analysis (FEA) used to model spacecraft structures, bond lines are frequently ignored or assumed to be an insignificant factor in defining the structural response of the system. The exact error associated with this assumption has not previously been well defined, especially for higher mode dynamic frequencies. Once quantified, this improved understanding of composite joining methods will allow designers to more accurately develop control algorithms for stiffness-critical applications.

PROPOSED RESEARCH APPROACH

This problem was studied using the following steps:

1. Conduct FEA parametric study of simple lap-shear bonded joint.
2. Develop a database of composite adherent and adhesive material properties.
3. Compare axial static stiffness predictions of FE model lap-shear joint to experiment.
4. Compare calculated dynamic response of a simple structural beam to experiment (utilize best method developed in static stiffness predictions from step #3).
5. Report best procedure for modeling bonds in stiffness-critical structures.

FEA PARAMETRIC STUDY OF BONDED JOINTS

Numerically characterizing the response of a bonded single lap joint using a variety of different configurations was the initial step in this study primarily in an effort to determine the extent of stiffness loss across a bonded joint. That is, the authors felt it worthwhile to identify the extent of the perceived problem prior to investing considerable time, effort, and expense into pursuing a solution. Because the objective of the present study was to determine if the presence of an adhesive bond in a stiffness critical composite structure degrades the stiffness of the entire structure, bond line thickness and adhesive stiffness were considered to be most influential. As a baseline model, a cantilevered single lap joint as shown in Figure 1 was modeled assuming an adhesive stiffness equal to the adherents (steel) and a bond line thickness of 0.127 mm. In addition, a parametric study was performed in which the thickness of the bond, adherent mechanical properties (steel), and adhesive mechanical properties were all varied to determine the influence on both the bond stiffness and structural system stiffness. More specifically for the parametric study, axial modulus values of 206.8, 20.68, 6.89 and 0.0207 GPa and bond line thickness values of 0.127, 381 and 3.18 mm were used in the present study. These values were selected to expose which parameter of a bonded lap joint most significantly reduces the stiffness of the bond when subjected to static and dynamic loading.

Figure 1. Finite element analysis model of a single lap bonded joint

All of the models previously described were numerically analyzed to determine the first ten modes of free vibration. For example, Figure 2 illustrates the 5th modal shape of a single lap joint containing a 0.127 mm bond thickness. Although the modal shape shown in Figure 2 indicates a complex geometric displacement, it is easily obtained using conventional FEA techniques. However, the absolute accuracy of the calculated mode shape is unknown since it was not experimentally verified. One significant result generated from this portion of the study was that the displaced mode shapes for all models studied varied dramatically, often being out of phase and plane for the same modal number. The significant changes found in modal displacements in the current study illustrate the sensitivity of even a simple bonded structure to bond line thickness and adhesive mechanical property variations.

Figure 2. Modal displacement of single lap joint, 0.127 mm bond thickness and generic adhesive material properties.

Of equal importance to the modal displacement variations found in the present study were the accompanying natural frequencies predicted for each of the cases. Calculated natural frequency deviated as much as 47% for the models analyzed in the present study, indicating that even for simple structures, neglecting the loss of stiffness associated with bonded joints can produce significant errors.

Figure 3 illustrates the differences in calculated natural frequencies associated with varying stiffness of a constant-thickness bond line. Similar results were obtained by varying the thickness of the bond line. Each natural frequency shown in Figure 3 was compared to the

baseline condition of equivalent bond and adherent stiffness, which represents the assumption of an infinitely rigid bond. As shown in Figure 3, neglecting the stiffness of the adhesive in a FEA analysis is probably acceptable for the first mode, but errors approaching 20% can be generated at higher modes. Compounding these estimated errors is that there was no discernable trend that describes the error associated with adhesive bonds as a function of modal frequency number, making it difficult to determine the severity to which an analytical model underestimates the stiffness of a structural system. These higher modes may be significant for applications requiring accurate displacement or high-frequency corrections, as are often needed in dynamic systems. These results clearly indicated to the authors that pursuing the effect of adhesive bond thickness and material type on structural stiffness was justified.

One subtle implication of these results found in the present study is that not only should bond line thickness and adhesive stiffness not be neglected, but also that accurate material characterization is required to avoid similar errors. That is, even if adhesive bonds are included in numerical models, failure to accurately characterize the adherends as well as the adhesive being used could potentially negate any improved modeling accuracy. For this reason, a complete material characterization was performed on IM7/977-2 carbon/epoxy and Hysol EA 9309.3NA adhesive material systems in the present study.

Figure 3. Comparison of Adhesively Bonded Joint (0.127 mm, 0.005 in thick bond line) Stiffness Error Compared to Baseline Case

MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION

The data presented in Figure 3 indicate the potential to generate significant numerical errors for higher modal predictions if the input material properties are inaccurate. Thus, considerable effort was exerted to accurately describe the behavior of the material systems over their entire useful operating range. This means the non-linear response of the constituent materials was also measured. The following paragraphs describe the results obtained from material tests of IM7/977-2 carbon/epoxy unidirectional prepreg and Hysol EA 9309.3NA adhesive. Constant,

linear, and second-order curve fits were utilized for all material properties to determine the most accurate representation of actual material response. Numerous standards have been developed that guide the characterization of materials⁷⁻¹¹. These standards combined with careful attention were used to develop the results presented here. For a more in-depth discussion of these results the reader is directed to reference 12.

With the considerable volume of experimental data presented in the reference 12, the authors offer as a summary of the recommended material properties as Table 1. Values shown in Table 1 represent the numerical descriptions, and regression limits, recommended for the materials in this study. The data in Table 1 completely describe the constant response of both IM7/977-2 carbon/epoxy unidirectional prepreg and Hysol EA 9309.3NA adhesive material systems. As previously discussed, depending on the FEA approach being implemented, it also completely describes the nonlinear response of the material systems. These data were used consistently throughout the course of this study. It should also be noted that density of the adhesive was found to be 1.17 g/cc as per ASTM Standard¹⁰.

Table 1. Summary of Recommended Material Property Values and Accompanying Strain Limits.

IM7/977-2	Constant Response	Nonlinear Response $\sigma, \tau \sim \text{Pa}, \epsilon, \gamma \sim \mu\epsilon$	Nonlinear Strain Limits
E ₁₁	173 GPa	$\sigma_{11} = 1.524\epsilon_{11}^2 + 1.670E5\epsilon_{11}$	$0 \leq \epsilon_{11} \leq 15,000 \mu\epsilon$
E ₂₂	9.17 GPa	$\sigma_{22} = -7.495E-2\epsilon_{22}^2 + 9.425\epsilon_{22}$	$0 \leq \epsilon_{22} \leq 7,250 \mu\epsilon$
E ₃₃	Same as E ₂₂	Same as E ₂₂	Same as E ₂₂
G ₁₂	5.65 GPa	$\tau_{12} = -0.146\gamma_{12}^2 + 6.481E3\gamma_{12}$	$0 \leq \gamma_{12} \leq 20,000 \mu\epsilon$
G ₂₃	3.30 GPa	N/A	N/A
G ₁₃	Same as G ₁₂	Same as G ₁₂	Same as G ₁₂
ν_{23}	Estimated = 0.5	N/A	N/A
ν_{13}	Same as ν_{12}	Same as ν_{12}	Same as ν_{12}
ν_{12}	0.34	$\nu_{12} = 0.335$	$0 \leq \epsilon_{11} \leq 500 \mu\epsilon$
density	1.63 (g/cc)	$\nu_{12} = -3.094E-3\epsilon_{11} + 0.3365$	$500 \leq \epsilon_{11} \leq 15,000 \mu\epsilon$
EA 9309			
E	2.55 GPa	$\sigma = -4.164E-2\epsilon^2 + 2964\epsilon$	$0 \leq \epsilon \leq 21,000 \mu\epsilon$
ν	0.389	$\nu = 1.116E-6\epsilon + 0.385$	$0 \leq \epsilon \leq 21,000 \mu\epsilon$
G	868 MPa	$\tau = -1.041E-2\gamma^2 + 1055\gamma$	$0 \leq \gamma \leq 40,000 \mu\epsilon$
density	1.17 (g/cc)		

STATIC STIFFNESS OF LAP-SHEAR JOINT

The next phase of research was focused on answering the question, “How should one model adhesive joints in stiffness-critical structures?” The first step in answering this question was to measure the axial static stiffness of a simple lap-joint test specimen and compare it to predictions from a simple finite element model¹³. To eliminate undesired rotation and moment effects in a traditional single-lap shear joint the Boeing Single Lap test specimen was used. This specimen is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Boeing single lap specimen (dimensions in inches)

Two separate tests were conducted on these specimens. In each test the steel grips are loaded into a universal testing machine and placed in tension. During the first test an extensometer was placed across one of the four adhesive bonds on each specimen. In the second test two strain gages were placed on each specimen. The first strain gage was placed on the center of one of the composite adherends while the other strain gage was placed in the center of the steel grips. The bond between one of the composite adherends and the metal grip was modeled in ABAQUS. The symmetry of the test geometry was utilized to reduce the complexity of the model as shown in Figure 5. Composite shell elements with offset section properties were used to model the composite laminate. Eight node brick elements were used to model the adhesive layer. The shell elements were connected directly to the adhesive layer, while the section properties were offset outward from the bond by half the adherend thickness on each side of the bond.

Figure 5. Finite Element Model of Boeing single lap specimen

Several parameters were varied to determine the most effective modeling procedure for predicting static axial stiffness of the bonded joint. The bond element type, mesh density through the bond thickness, and in-plane mesh density were varied in the finite element model. In addition, results computed utilizing non-linear material properties were compared to those obtained utilizing linear material properties.

The results indicate that in this model the static axial stiffness is not sensitive to the bond element type. Similarly, the model showed little sensitivity to either the number of elements through the bond thickness or to the in-plane mesh density. Therefore, it is assumed that one 8

node brick element through the adhesive bond line is sufficient to predict axial static stiffness in a lap-shear bond line.

The incorporation of non-linear material properties into the model yielded some improvement in the correlation between the model and experiment. In addition when nonlinear geometric effects were used in the model a slightly improved correlation was achieved. Therefore, it is recommended that nonlinear material properties and geometry are used to calculate stiffness in a single-lap shear joint.

DYNAMIC RESPONSE OF A SIMPLE STRUCTURAL BEAM

The next step in this study was to compare the calculated dynamic response of a simple structural beam to the experimentally measured response¹³. In this study two different beam configurations were studied, that is (1) with a lap shear bond in the center of the beam, and (2) no bond in the beam. The initial approach to calculate the dynamic response was to use the best techniques determined in the previous static stiffness predictions; that is one eight node brick element through the adhesive thickness with nonlinear material properties and geometric effects taken into account. The simple structural beam was designed to be representative of a very stiff optical platform; i.e. first bending mode frequency near 40 Hz. It was also designed to be relatively easy to fabricate and test, and to have a large difference in dynamic response between the bonded beam and the no-bond beam over a wide range of modes.

A parametric study was conducted utilizing a finite element model to determine the significant factors influencing the dynamic behavior of the beam. The parameters that were studied included boundary conditions (free-free and fixed-free), bond location in the beam, bond length, end plate (mass and geometry), beam length, beam thickness, and ply orientation. The significant results of this study were that a shorter, cylindrical beam with less, but equal tip masses, thicker composite adherends, and small ply angles was affected to a greater degree by the presence of a bonded joint. Asymmetry with respect to the tips masses results in higher natural frequencies for each mode and variation of bond position. Variation of the bond position along the beam length had little effect on the resulting frequency response (with the exception of the first bending mode in the fixed-free configuration). The final configuration developed is shown in Figure 6.

The dynamic testing on this structure was conducted in two phases. First, a low bandwidth test was conducted with tri-axial accelerometers that had an upper limit frequency response of 3 kHz. These accelerometers were placed at 20 locations on the beam. This test provided data from which the natural frequencies and the associated mode shapes could be extracted for each of the modes up to 3 kHz. The next test was conducted utilizing high bandwidth uni-axial accelerometers that were placed at the same locations as the tri-axial accelerometers in the first test. These uni-axial accelerometers have an upper limit frequency response of 10 kHz. Mode frequencies between 3 kHz and 10 kHz are apparent with these tests; however, the mode shapes cannot be determined from these accelerometers.

These tests were repeated for both fixed-free and free-free boundary conditions. The fixed-free boundary condition was accomplished by bolting the beam vertically to a rigid optics table that was in turn bolted and bonded to the concrete floor. The free-free boundary condition test was accomplished by suspending the beam with thin, lightweight, rubber cords. The beam was

excited through single-point excitation with an instrumented hammer. An accelerometer placed at the point of impact measured the input forcing function.

Figure 6. Structural Beam Configuration

The first parameter examined was element type for both the fixed-free and free-free boundary conditions. The results of this study are summarized in Figure 7 and 8. In these figures the element names are the ABAQUS element types. These plots indicate the type of element used for the bond has greater impact on the predicted dynamic response than does the type of shell element used for the composite. It is apparent that the reduced integration, eight node, hexagonal element (C3D8R) is the most efficient element choice. This element uses lower order integration to form the element stiffness matrix while full integration is used to form the mass matrix. The similarity between the predicted natural frequencies and mode shapes provided verification for the modeling produces used.

Figure 7. Sensitivity of element type (fixed-free boundary conditions)

Figure 8. Sensitivity of element type (free-free boundary conditions)

Next, using this well correlated model, results were computed for the no-bond case and compared to the previous results for the bonded beam. These results are summarized in Figure 9 for the fixed-free conditions (similar results are available for the free-free conditions¹³). This figure indicates that bonds affect a structure most significantly in the lower modes. However, the errors in the higher modes resulting from neglecting the effect of bonds can be significant, especially for structures requiring very high dimensional stability.

Figure 9. Natural frequencies of bonded and un-bonded beams (fixed-free boundary conditions)

CONCLUSIONS

General guidelines can now be specified when considering the effect of bonded joints on the dynamic response of a structure.

- Bonds should be included in the finite element model when the structures are very stiff, the bond is in the center of a free-free beam, or at the fixed end of fixed-free beam, and the bond line is thick. Neglecting the bonds may cause errors in predicted natural frequency of 15-25%.
- One element through the bond line is sufficient. Reduced integration hexagonal elements in the bond line produce the best results for a given computational cost.
- Reduced integration shell elements should be used for the composite adherends. This formulation provides adequate accuracy with good computational efficiency.
- Offset shell section properties are recommended for the adherends. It is important to verify the offset directions; significant errors can result if these directions are not used correctly.

It would be desirable to develop a bond element that could be used to model bonds in large, complex composite structures. This element would eliminate the complications of meshing thin bond lines and the associated problems of high aspect ratio elements or very dense meshes. This work has laid the foundation for future work toward this direction by providing an experimentally verified model which can be used in future studies.

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